

TRAINING MODULE

ON PROVIDING ADEQUATE SERVICES
TO LGBTIQ CHILDREN IN VULNERABLE CONTEXTS

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FOREWORD

LGBTIQ children need the support of those professionals who work directly with them on a daily basis. These professionals include teachers, social and health workers, psychologists, and others in the care sector and children's services. LGBTIQ children need this support in order to build resilience in the face of social barriers arising from a low level of understanding of their needs. This publication aims to assist trainers who seek to enhance the capacities of the aforementioned groups of professionals, so that these professionals can better understand and provide adequate services to LGBTIQ children in vulnerable contexts, with a particular focus on the post-Covid-19 environment.

The training module considers the main findings of the field research for the "Colourful Childhoods" project, which explored the needs of LGBTIQ children in vulnerable contexts in Bulgaria, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, and Spain. It also looked at questions of resilience in response to the Covid-19 context.

The four-hour intensive training workshop incorporates training techniques targeted at adult learners. The training aims to facilitate active learning and interaction between the trainer(s) and the trainees, as well as among the trainees themselves. Each trainer is encouraged to make necessary adjustments and adaptations based on their own experience and skills, the national/social context in which they are working, the selection of topics they wish to focus on, and the profile and background of their trainees.

This module is based on field-tested training materials that were developed within EU-funded projects worked on by partners in this consortium. These projects are: Diversity and Childhood, CHOICE, BringIn, and Come Forward. The learning materials have been further developed and adapted to the objectives of Colourful Childhoods project.

Monika Pisankaneva
Bilitis Foundation

OVERVIEW OF THE TRAINING WORKSHOP

Method: Training techniques for adult learners.

Target groups:

- Teachers and school professionals who work directly with children in public or private schools.
- Social care professionals (psychologists, social workers, speech and language specialists) working directly with children in public social services, or in private practice.
- Health care professionals (doctors, nurses, hospital personnel) working directly with children in public or private hospitals / clinics, or in private practices.
- Youth and community workers, leisure professionals and other professionals in children's services working directly with children and youth.

Number and profile of participants per training workshop: 20, in mixed groups.

Total duration: 4 hours.

The Training Workshop is made up of 3 sessions. It is developed for face-to-face training. However, the exercises can be easily adjusted to an online environment by using a platform which allows participants to be divided into small work groups (or 'breakout' groups).

Session 1 begins with participant introductions, and an introduction to the learning objectives for the training as a whole. It also serves to explore participants' expectations in relation to the training, as well as their level of understanding of key concepts related to SOGIESC (sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression and sex characteristics). Finally, it allows participants to explore their attitudes towards non-cisgender and non-heterosexual individuals, both adults and children.

Session 2 aims to familiarize participants with their own national legal frameworks on LGBTIQ rights, especially in relation to the prevention of LGBTIQ violence and hate crimes. Furthermore, it raises awareness of the deficiencies of these frameworks, as well as of situations in which the existence of legal measures is not sufficient to prevent wrongdoing. It includes small group work on specific case studies, followed by a presentation of the relevant legal frameworks.

Session 3 aims to raise participants' awareness their personal role in developing an LGBTIQ-inclusive environment as professionals working directly with children. This helps create a more proactive attitude towards the prevention of anti-LGBTIQ violence, and supports non-discrimination and inclusion. The final session presents a set of tools and good practices that participants can learn from and use in their own professional practice. As this is the closing session, it includes a wrap-up of the training, and time for evaluation.

STRUCTURE OF THE 4-HOUR TRAINING WORKSHOP

Session 1: Introduction and Exploring Knowledge on SOGIESC	Duration
Welcome Presentation of the learning objectives and contents of the training	10 min
Introductions and icebreaker	10 min
Exploring expectations and Setting Ground Rules	15 min
Basic concepts: Exploring the understanding of key concepts that will be used in the training; presentation of 20 Key Concepts	30 min
Self-reflection exercise on attitudes towards LGBTIQ people	30 min
BREAK	5 min
Session 2: LGBTIQ Rights in the National Context	Duration
Group Work on Case Studies	30 min
National Legal Framework on Prevention and Dealing with anti-LGBTIQ hate crimes, school bullying, including cyber-bullying: Presentation and discussion	30 min
BREAK	5 min

Session 3: Creating a Safe Environment for LGBTIQ Children: How Can We Help as Professionals?	Duration
Tools and good practices to identify, prevent and combat violence against LGBTIQ children: Presentation	30 min
My Role as an Educator / Social Worker / Health Professional / Professional in Children's Services in Creating an LGBTIQ-Inclusive Environment	30 min
BREAK	5 min
Closing Session. Wrap-up and evaluation Filling in Online Evaluation Forms	25 min

SESSION 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPLORING PRE-EXISTING KNOWLEDGE ON SOGIESC

Learning Outcomes:

- Participants get to know each other.
- Participants are involved in active learning.
- Participants are able to define, understand, and apply the basic concepts included in the LGBTIQ acronym, and become aware of their own attitudes towards sexual orientation, and gender / gender identity diversity.

ACTIVITY 1: WELCOME, PRESENTATION OF LEARNING OBJECTIVES, AND INTRODUCTION TO THE CONTENT OF THE TRAINING

Presentation by the Workshop Facilitator(s).

Participants' Self-Introduction: A quick round of introductions, allowing participants to share their name and organizational affiliation.

ACTIVITY 2: BREAKING THE ICE

Guidelines for trainer(s):

- A method to easily break the ice and let trainees get to know each other is to divide participants into groups of 4 or 5 and ask each group to find 10 things that everyone in the group has in common. The 10 things should be applicable to all group members and should identify things that lie outside obvious traits or characteristics — e.g., that all group members are human.
- Next, each group will be given 3-5 minutes to introduce the 10 things they have in common to the rest of the group. They will also be encouraged to share the process by means of which they came to agreement on this list. Was it difficult? Did they enjoy it?

One advantage of this method is that it avoids the anxiety and/or embarrassment that can be produced by other methods, such as that of the self-introduction in a group of strangers.

ACTIVITY 3: EXPECTATIONS AND FEARS

Guidelines for trainer(s):

- All participants receive two different colored pieces sticky paper notes (for example, Post-It notes). Each group should have the same two colours. One colour will be used for recording expectations, and the other for recording fears.
- Ask the participants to write down on the respective pieces of paper their expectations for what they will learn from the training workshops, and what their fears are. Give them three minutes.
- When they have finished, ask them to place their notes on a flipchart pad divided in advance into two parts: fears and expectations.
- After discussing participants' expectations and fears, identify which are the most common and discuss these with the group to draw some preliminary conclusions.
- Keep the flipchart until the end of the session, in a place that can be seen by all participants.

ACTIVITY 4: GROUND RULES

Guidelines for trainer(s):

- Start a new flipchart page, making sure all participants can see it.
- Ask participants to think for 2-3 minutes about what rules would **a) facilitate their learning process, and b) help encourage the active participation of everyone in the group.**

Some examples:

- Maintain mutual respect among all participants.
- Avoid interrupting other participants.
- Express your opinion, and/or disagreement in a respectful manner.
- Keep your mobile phone switched off, or on "silent mode".
- No smoking, drinking or eating during the training activities.
- Be on time every day of the training.
- After participants have had a chance to think of ideas, encourage them to share these ideas, and write them on the flipchart pad.
- You may suggest your own ideas and add them to the flipchart.
- After all the ideas from the group have been recorded on the flipchart, work with the group to establish a learning contract based on an agreement about which ideas/suggestions are collectively most important.
- As with the fears and expectations flipchart from the earlier exercise, the learning agreement flipchart can be placed somewhere where it can be seen by everyone for the remainder of the training.

ACTIVITY 5: KEY CONCEPTS

Learning outcomes:

- Become familiar with relevant terminology.
- Understand the differences between terms that are often confused.
- Combat ignorance, stereotypes and prejudices against LGBTIQ people.

CHECKING THE UNDERSTANDING OF THE KEY CONCEPTS RELATED TO LGBTIQ.

Most professionals are familiar with the acronym LGBTIQ, but they do not necessarily understand these concepts well. While “gay”, “lesbian” and “bisexual” are commonly used and their meaning is widely known, some professionals may struggle with understanding “trans”, “non-binary”, “intersex” and “queer”.

Guidelines for trainer(s):

- Begin with a 10-question quiz to test trainees’ understanding and knowledge of key concepts related to LGBTIQ topics.
- Distribute the “**5 questions on understanding**” handout (ANNEX 1) with the 5 questions listed below. Give participants up to 5 minutes to fill in the answers to questions 1 to 5. Participants may need less time, so check if everyone is ready after the third minute. If not, continue to the full 5 minutes.
- Ask participants to fold their handouts and place them on the table. Then take a random handout and read the answer out loud. Discuss each answer with the group. If an answer is false, ask others in the group to explain why. Give space for participants to share their perspectives, and take the floor only if no one knows the right answer. If an answer is correct, congratulate the group.

THE FIRST 5 QUESTIONS WILL CHECK THEIR UNDERSTANDING(ANNEX 1).

1. The terms “sexual orientation”, “gender identity” and “sex characteristics” are:

- Synonyms, as they all refer to a person’s specific set of characteristics
- Different, and they are not necessarily related nor does each one imply anything about the others (correct answer)
- Different, but they are related and each one necessarily implies something about the others

2. “Maria is a trans woman” means:

- Maria identifies as a woman, but her gender identity is male.
- Maria identifies as a woman: her gender identity is female. However, at birth her assigned sex was male. (correct answer)
- Maria has both male and female sex characteristics, but she has chosen to identify as a woman.

3. The fact that someone is intersex:

- Will not necessarily become apparent: it is possible that some intersex people never find out at all.
- Will necessarily become apparent at prenatal stage or at birth at the latest, as soon as it becomes clearly visible to medical staff.
- Will necessarily become apparent, but this could be at different times in life: at birth, during childhood, in puberty or even in adulthood. (correct answer)

4. When speaking with transgender children, the teacher / health worker / social worker should:

- Refer to them with their legal name because this is what is required in their role as a service-provider.
- Be aware both of the trans child’s legal name and the name the trans child has chosen for themselves and ask them which name should be used in public.
- Refer to them with the name that the trans child has chosen for themselves. (correct answer)

5. Asking about the pronouns that should be used when speaking with a trans / intersex child:

- Is not necessary because as a professional, I am obliged to refer to them with the pronoun that suits their legal name.
- Is a necessary first step for creating trust between the teacher/social/health worker and the trans/intersex child. (correct answer)
- It is not considered correct to ask about the pronouns that others prefer to use for themselves. Instead, we should always speak to students/patients using the polite form in plural.

THE NEXT 5 QUESTIONS WILL CHECK THEIR ATTITUDES / BELIEFS.

Distribute the Handout “5 questions on beliefs” (ANNEX 2) and ask participants to read it and individually fill in the answers. When participants have finished, do not collect the handouts. Instead, read out loud each question and provide the right answer together with an explanation. Each participant will compare their answer to the one provided by the facilitator.

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements? You will need to explain why.

1. **I do not see how knowing that a student/participant/patient is lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans or intersex might affect my role at work.**
 - (Explain that being LGBTIQ has a strong influence on a child's experience in school and may lead to internalized homo/bi/trans/inter-phobia, which obstructs the child's development. Also, anti-LGBTIQ violence / bullying is often invisible. A teacher/social worker/health worker should be aware if a child is L.G.B.T.I, or Q, in order to provide the most adequate support to the student/patient).
2. **A teacher / health / social / children's services worker should always use the word “parent” instead of “mother/father” when asking their students / participants / patients about their family relations.**
 - (This is a good way to avoid misgendering a parent and also encourages the child to share, if they live in a Rainbow Family).
3. **I should always ask about the sexual orientation / gender identity of a student/participant/patient who tells me about a bullying incident that happened to them in the school.**
 - (Yes, a teacher/social worker/health worker should find a non-intrusive way of asking about SOGIESC in order to determine the cause of the incident. If it appears that the incident was motivated by anti-LGBTIQ sentiments, the professional working with the victim should inform the relevant authorities and seek help in eliminating the root cause of the problem).
4. **The LGBTIQ perspective should be an integral part of every teacher/health worker/social/children's services worker's professional training.**
 - (Yes, understanding the LGBTIQ identities helps teachers/social workers/health workers to provide more adequate support to students/clients/patients who have suffered from anti-LGBTIQ discrimination or violence, or internalized homo-bi/trans/inter-phobia).
5. **When speaking about LGBTIQ people, professionals need to be aware that there are social disadvantages and challenges that may not be completely visible to others.**
 - (Yes, the SOGIESC of a child/person are not always visible. Cis-hetero-framing sends a message to all children who are LGBTIQ that their identities are “not normal” or “not acceptable” and causes psychological trauma. Teachers, social workers, and health workers should avoid assuming all children they work with are cisgender and heterosexual, and they should provide space to students/clients/patients for sharing personal information about their identities).

After the quiz, give the handout Handout “Twenty Key Concepts” (Annex 3) to the trainees and briefly present the 20 concepts in outline. Invite participants to refer to the resources presented at the end of the session for further information.

ACTIVITY 6: REFLECTION ON SEXUAL ORIENTATION, SEX CHARACTERISTICS, AND GENDER IDENTITY

Expected learning outcomes

After this module, trainees should be able to:

- Reflect on attitudes towards sexual orientation, sex characteristics, and gender diversity.
- Better understand the impact of heteronormative / cis-normative attitudes and know how to tackle heteronormativity and cis-normativity in daily life.
- Answer questions relating to sexual and gender diversity and normativity.
- Better understand these topics and help spread knowledge about them.
- Build the necessary skills to react to LGBTIQ myths with more confidence and overcome the LGBTIQ-related stereotypes.

Divide the members of the group into pairs. Give the pairs the following questions for reflection. Encourage them to find a comfortable space for discussion anywhere within the training space. After 15 min, the pairs should come back, and share their reflections with the whole group.

Questions for Reflection

1. Do you feel like you have any advantages or disadvantages because of your assigned gender? Which ones?
2. Do you feel that you must act a certain way because of your gender?
3. What happens if or when you don't act that way?
4. How do you talk about LGBTIQ people? Do you talk about LGBTIQ people in the same way you talk about straight or cisgender people? Or do you talk about them differently?
5. Have you ever felt judged in some way because of the way you express yourself and dress? (In which situations? How have people reacted to you on these occasions? How has that made you feel?).
6. Do you think that LGBTIQ people are judged by others because of their differences from the hetero-cis-gender norms? If so, how?
7. Do you think sexual orientation and gender identity are a choice? Why (not)?
8. Are LGBTIQ identities pathological? Can they be "cured" / changed?
9. Do LGBTIQ people suffer from discrimination? Which of their rights are not secured in your country?
10. Do you think that LGBTIQ Pride events are needed, or not? Why, in your opinion, are they organized?

Debriefing: 10 minutes

After the group reconvenes, the facilitator asks the participants about their experience of this reflection task, and how they now feel. The facilitator then asks some of the participants to share their reflections, and to talk about whether they reached an agreement with their discussion partner, or whether they maintained different opinions.

Tips for Trainers on the Questions in this exercise

The final 4 questions in the exercise often raise controversy and debate. If you are asked to reflect on these questions you may find the following pointers useful to guide the discussion:

Answer to Question 7: Do you think sexual orientation and gender identity are a choice? Why?

No, sexual orientation and gender identity are not the result of a decision or ongoing daily effort. Professional mental health organizations, including the American Psychological Association, have issued statements explaining that sexual orientation is not a choice and cannot be changed at will. What is a choice for some LGBTBI people is to come out of the closet, or disclose their gender or sexuality. This coming out process not a one-time event, and when it occurs in hostile environments, it may cause a backlash.

Answer to Question 8: Are Are LGBTIQ identities pathological? Can they be “cured” / changed?

Since having a non-heterosexual orientation is not a disease or disorder, it cannot be “cured”. Professional, scientific and medical organizations condemn “reparative” or “conversion” therapy as ineffective and psychologically harmful. Trans identities are also not considered pathological and cannot be “cured”/ changed. Intersex variations are still categorized as pathological variations of sex development from the World Health Organization, despite the fact that “normalizing” medical intervention has been condemned by many international bodies, including the United Nations Committee against Torture and the Council of Europe.

Answer to Question 9: Do LGBTIQ people suffer from discrimination? Which of their rights are not secured in your country?

LGBTIQ persons still suffer from discrimination, and attitudes towards LGBTIQ persons are still be often negative. The extent and kind of discrimination depends on the sociopolitical context of each country and period. Discrimination can be expressed in laws, guidelines, through distorted media images and information, through withholding information (like in school textbooks) and through negative attitudes and behavior (name calling, jokes).

LGBTIQ people may face different kinds of discrimination, depending on how open they are about their identities. People who choose to not be out may face less direct discrimination that those who are out. However, not coming out doesn't guarantee LGBTIQ people will be safe from discrimination. They can still face indirect discrimination (e.g., by hearing negative comments about LGBTIQ people in general or by seeing other people being discriminated against). Furthermore, even if still “in the closet”, LGTBQI people can be targets of discrimination if others suspect them to be LGBTIQ. Furthermore, choosing to stay in the closet is also not an option for many people, especially trans people.

Everyone should have the right to be safe, without having to conceal their true self.

Answer to Question 10: Do you think that LGBTIQ Pride events are needed, or not? Why are they organized in your opinion?

LGBTIQ Pride is the positive stance against discrimination and violence toward lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex people. Pride promotes self-affirmation, dignity and equality of rights, while building community, increasing the visibility of LGBTIQ communities, and celebrating sexual diversity and gender variance.

In some countries, Pride takes the form of a celebration. In others, it is also a political act, a way of pointing out that not all citizens are treated equally, and that there are groups of people whose rights are not secured.

Gay Pride commemorates the Stonewall riots. In the early hours of June 28, 1969, police raided the Stonewall Inn bar in New York City's Greenwich Village. The political uprising that followed, known as the Stonewall riots, led to the first Pride event.

Pride typically involves a series of community and public events, and often culminates in a parade involving marchers and colorful floats from the LGBTQ community and its supporters. Before the Stonewall riots, LGBTIQ individuals didn't generally broadcast their sexual orientation or identity. But the events after the police raid on the Stonewall Inn bar galvanized the gay community and sparked greater political activism.

Early Pride events (often called Freedom Day or Gay Liberation Day) were often sparsely attended and encountered protests, particularly because of the outlandish costumes that some marchers wore. The courageous refusal to follow social norms — through sometimes outlandish public displays of LGBTIQ identities — inevitably attracted counter-protests. But these political acts were instrumental in bringing about a social transformation that eventually led to a greater acceptance of diverse identities.

In 1978, what is perhaps the most-recognized symbol of Gay Pride made its debut at the San Francisco event: the rainbow flag. The flag, with its eight colors (sexuality symbolized by hot pink, life by red, healing by orange, the sun by yellow, nature by green, art by blue, harmony by indigo, and spirit by violet), was designed by San Francisco artist Gilbert Baker. The flag has since been adopted worldwide.

Session 1 resources for preparation and/or additional study:

- Human Rights Campaign (n.d.). "Glossary of Terms". Retrieved from: <https://www.hrc.org/resources/glossary-of-terms>
- ILGA Europe (2015). Glossary. Retrieved from: https://www.ilga-europe.org/sites/default/files/glossary_october_2015_edition.pdf
- LGBTIQA Resource Center (n.d.). "Glossary". Retrieved from: <https://LGBTIQA.ucdavis.edu/educated/glossary>
- TGEU (2016). "Glossary". Retrieved from: <https://tgeu.org/glossary/>
- United Nations – Free & Equal (n.d.). "Definitions". Retrieved from: <https://www.unfe.org/definitions/>

SESSION 2. LGBTIQ RIGHTS IN THE NATIONAL CONTEXT

Outcomes:

- Establish a foundation of basic knowledge about relevant national legal provisions related to SOGIESC.
- Understand the basic concepts of discrimination, hate crime and hate speech, on the grounds of sexual orientation, gender identity, and sex characteristics, and the differences between them, as well as how they are interlinked.
- Develop an awareness of LGBTIQ rights as an aspect of (acknowledged and internationally protected) human rights.
- Become familiar with procedures for reporting anti-LGBTIQ hate crimes and bullying, including cyber bullying.

ACTIVITY 1: WORKING IN GROUPS – CASE STUDY

Guidelines for trainer(s):

- Based on the national legal framework of your own country, to the best of your knowledge, does this case constitute a violation of law? Please, explain your answer.
- Beyond the national legal framework of your own country, do you think this case constitutes a violation of human rights? Please, explain your answer.
- If this case constitutes a violation of law, based on your understanding of your own national context, how would somebody file an official complaint or report?
 - Now ask each group to present to the whole group the case they have explored, as well as their reflections on each question. Give each group 5 minutes.
 - After each presentation, invite the whole group to respond to what they have heard, and to contribute their own perspectives.

CASE STUDY. IMPORTANT NOTICE FOR TRAINERS:

- Design interesting cases that are plausible and reflect the current social context.
- Ask trainees to read the case study at the beginning of the small group discussions, and to ask questions if there is anything that is unclear to them.
- Connect these case studies with the knowledge trainees have already gained during the workshop.
- Allow and encourage participants to connect their assigned case study with their own experiences as professionals.

ACTIVITY 2: NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Guidelines for trainer(s):

- Prepare a 10-15 minutes (at most) presentation on your national legal framework with regard to:
 - Hate crime, hate speech, and discrimination on grounds of sex characteristics.
 - Identity-based school bullying against LGBTIQ groups, including cyber bullying.
 - Children's rights and the status of LGBTIQ children.
 - Patients' rights with an emphasis on self-determination of gender identity, bodily integrity, and informed consent.
 - Penalties in case of violations.
 - Available official reporting channels (e.g., police, ombudsmen, etc.) and basic information regarding reporting procedures.
 - Reporting platforms managed by LGBTIQ organisations or other NGOs.
- The relevant provisions of international/European legal frameworks in relation to the human rights of LGBTIQ people.
- Distribute hard or electronic copies of your (adapted) presentation to all trainees for reference.

ACTIVITY 3: DISCUSSION

Optional questions for the trainers to facilitate in-depth understanding of policies that prevent and combat anti-LGBTIQ hate crimes, school and cyber bullying:

1. Questions for all professionals: Are you aware of any national reports on anti-LGBTIQ hate crimes? If yes, which is the most frequently reported type of anti-LGBTIQ crimes in your country? What types of hate crimes are recognised in your country? Please list them. Does the state keep statistics on anti-LGBTIQ crimes? Do you think keeping a record of such crimes is important to ensure adequate support for victims, and the prevention of future incidents?

2. Questions for teachers and school personnel: Does the school you work in have an anti-bullying policy? Does this policy require every incident is recorded? Are identity-based factors noted when recording incidents? Is there an anonymous channel for reporting incidents in your school? How likely are you to report an incident which includes only verbal harassment towards an LGBTIQ child (such as calling them names, joking about their sex life, etc.)?
3. Questions for health/social/child services workers: Have you come across children in your practice who show signs of having being subjected to violence? Are you obliged to report to the law-enforcement institutions when you see that a child has been subject to violence? If yes, do you ask the child to provide more information about the incident? Is there a special service in your institution for children who have been victims of violence?
4. Questions for all professionals: Have you ever heard about children who are victims of cyber bullying? If you are contacted for help by a child who is subject to cyber bullying, do you have an obligation to report the incident(s)? To whom would you report? Is there a special reporting tool for bullying/harassment at your workplace? Does this reporting tool allow for the anonymous reporting of incidents? Can it be used by both clients and staff?

During the discussion, the facilitator can reference established procedures and good practices for dealing with incidents of anti-LGBTIQ hate crimes, school bullying, and cyber bullying.

Session 2 resources for preparation and/or additional study:

- Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A12012P%2FTXT>
- Ghattas, D. C. (2019). Protecting intersex people in Europe: a toolkit for law and policymakers. With digital appendix and checklist, ILGA Europe & OII Europe. Retrieved from: https://oiieurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Protecting_intersex_in_Europe_toolkit.pdf
- European Convention on Human Rights as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14 supplemented by Protocols Nos. 1, 4, 6, 7, 12, 13 and 16. Retrieved from: https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/convention_eng.pdf
- European Convention for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, Strasbourg, 26.XI.1987. Retrieved from: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/rms/090000168007a67f>
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights FRA (2015). Protection against discrimination on grounds of sexual orientation, gender identity and sex characteristics in the EU – Comparative legal analysis – Update 2015, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Retrieved from: https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/protection_against_discrimination_legal_update_2015.pdf

- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights FRA (2015). The fundamental rights situation of intersex people, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Retrieved from: https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2015-focus-04-intersex_en.pdf
- European Social Charter, Turin, 18.X.1961. Retrieved from: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/rms/0900000168006b642>
- ILGA Europe (2021). Rainbow Index 2021. Retrieved from: <https://www.ilga-europe.org/files/uploads/2022/04/Rainbow-Europe-Index-2021.pdf>
- United Nations, Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted and opened for signature, ratification and accession by General Assembly resolution 44/25 of 20 November 1989 entry into force 2 September 1990, in accordance with article 49. Retrieved from: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/crc.aspx>
- United Nations (1948). The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Retrieved from: <https://www.un.org/en/universal-declaration-human-rights/>

SESSION 3. CREATING A SAFE ENVIRONMENT FOR LGBTIQ CHILDREN: HOW CAN WE HELP AS PROFESSIONALS?

Learning Outcomes:

- Understand and raise awareness regarding the status of LGBTIQ children and the multiple challenges they face.
- Enhance empathy for LGBTIQ children and understanding of LGBTIQ issues through first-hand experience.
- Understand the role of professionals who are in direct contact with children (teachers, health and social workers).

ACTIVITY 1: PLENARY DISCUSSION. THE STATUS OF LGBTIQ CHILDREN IN VULNERABLE CONTEXTS.

Tools and good practices to identify, prevent, and combat violence against LGBTIQ children. The provision of support and adequate services in Covid and post-Covid contexts.

Guidelines for trainer(s):

- Lead a discussion with all trainees on the status of LGBTIQ children in their country. Encourage trainees to share thoughts, knowledge and experience relating to the issue. Questions may include, but are not limited to: (lived experience)
 - What do you know about LGBTIQ children in your country? What do you know about this population: for example, number of children, social/demographic profile etc.?
 - What factors do you need to pay particular attention to when working with LGBTIQ children, and how may these factors be different from those that you need to consider when working with LGBTIQ adults?
 - From your knowledge and/or experience, would you say LGBTIQ children are usually treated with equality and respect in your environment? Why/why not?
 - What do you think are the main challenges LGBTIQ children face?

- What do you think the impact of Covid-19 has been on the lives of children in general, and of LGBTIQ children in particular?
- Are there any lasting consequences for LGBTIQ children of the Covid-19 pandemic and the associated restrictions?
- Have Covid and post-Covid contexts led to an increased risk of violence/cyberviolence for LGBTIQ children?

ACTIVITY 2: GENERAL GUIDANCE FOR PROFESSIONALS WHO WORK DIRECTLY WITH LGBTIQ CHILDREN VICTIMS OF VIOLENCE

If you are a professional who works directly with an LGBTIQ child who shows signs of experiencing violence, you can provide support and encourage the child to seek help with overcoming any trauma brought about by the incident. Below are some basic guidelines for professionals and/or supporting services/departments:

- Use of appropriate, non-abusive and inclusive language.
- Include a third option in addition to man or woman in all your working documents.
- Never ask questions simply to satisfy your curiosity.
- Treat LGBTIQ children with empathy, discretion and respect towards their personal story and the challenges they may have faced.
- Always use the name and pronouns the LGBTIQ child uses to self-identify.

Get to know which LGBTIQ, human rights and/or equality bodies and organizations support LGBTIQ children, so that you can make referrals according to the child's assessed needs.

- Use your website, social media accounts, etc. to spread the message that your organization/institution/service doesn't discriminate on the grounds of sexual orientation, gender identity or sex characteristics.
- Make use of the support of LGBTIQ organizations and activists to acquire educational/awareness material, and/or to organize training and awareness-raising activities for you and your colleagues.
- Create and maintain a referral network of organizations, bodies and institutions that support LGBTIQ children (e.g., LGBTIQ organizations, equality bodies, etc.) so you can facilitate access to additional support services.

The Colourful Childhoods project will produce guidelines and protocols that can prevent and combat violence against LGBTIQ children in vulnerable contexts. These guidelines will be freely available on the project website.

PRESENTATION 1: CYBER BULLYING – MAIN RISK FACTORS, SEXTING, HOW TO REACT

Cyber bullying is the use of the internet to inflict emotional harm on others. It is frequently used by children and teenagers as a means of causing offence and harm, retaliating in disputes, or as a means of “joking” with friends. Cyber bullying can take different forms: creating fake Facebook profiles, posting derogatory or demeaning photos or videos on sites like YouTube, or sending abusive or threatening messages via Messenger, Viber or WhatsApp.

Cyber bullying:

- Can be done from any device connected to the internet (smartphone, laptop, computer);
- Is often directed at a more vulnerable classmate (for example, a classmate of a different ethnicity, or who looks and behaves differently from the norm);
- May start as an attempt to prank, but may also be targeted revenge;
- Can happen 24/7 because the internet is available anywhere, anytime;
- Has a potentially much greater reach than simply the immediate circle of the victim's classmates and friends. When content is uploaded to the internet, it is freely available for anyone to see;
- Can cause a reluctance to go to school and to socialise with peers, a fear of internet use, isolation from others, anxiety, and bodily symptoms such as headaches and stomach aches.

In case of cyber bullying:

- It is recommended that the child ends the conversation with the person who is harassing them, and stops following their posts and comments. The best option is for the victim to block the profile of the person or people in question, and report both the profile and the abusive or bullying content.
- Although the most visible participants are the victim and the abuser (and the supporters of the bully), other people are involved in cyber bullying as witnesses.
- Take steps to make sure the child doesn't close themselves off. One of the most important things is to stay open. The existence of friends or a good friendship group can be beneficial in this.

Sexting is the exchange of messages, photos or videos with sexual content between two partners. The word is made up of the words "sex" and "texting". Sexting most often contains nude pictures, but it can also contain clips of masturbation or sexual intercourse. It is practiced by both adults and teenagers, and sometimes children. It is common for sexting to occur voluntarily in a peer-to-peer relationship or flirtation. But if such photos or videos are shared with others, it can lead to harassment in the real world and on the internet. An adult sexting a child or teenager is also called "grooming".

In case of sexting:

- The user who distributed the photo must be blocked and reported to the site administrators. We also recommend that the photo or video should be reported.
- Those working with the child should open a space for them to talk about their experience freely without shame.
- Further actions will depend on the national legislation. But in most national contexts, the dissemination of child pornography is considered a crime, and should be reported to the police.

PRESENTATION 2: HOW TO TALK ABOUT AN INCIDENT WITH AN LGBTIQ CHILD WHO IS A VICTIM

If you are the first/only adult the child trusts to talk to, you can talk with the child and try to obtain as much information about the incident as possible. This information can be used to put in place an adequate level of support for the victim.

Steps to be followed during the interview/talk:

- Explain to the victim how you will use the information about the incident. It is important that the child is always accompanied by a person familiar to them.
- Give the victim your job contacts (mobile, email, etc.) so that the child can reach you after the talk.
- Ask what the child prefers to be called, and use this name to build respect, rapport and trust.
- Ask the child if there are any physical injuries and make sure that medical assistance is available.
- Explain to the child what the consequences could be for the offender, and what type of support the child can obtain as a victim of violence. Make sure the information you provide is simple, accessible, and understandable.
- Always make sure the child feels safe and confident. Let them know they can ask questions if there is anything they don't understand.
- Be aware that the victim should share only the information they want to share. This is particularly important if your initial contact with the child is immediately after they experienced violence.
- Acknowledge the victim's experience by thanking them for sharing it with you. Reassure the child about confidentiality during and after the talk.
- If possible, inform the child about further steps to be taken, and your role in these.
- Make an individual assessment: Does the child have any specific support or protection needs? Is the child particularly vulnerable to repeated violence or secondary victimization[1]? Based on this, you can decide whether you need to bring information about the case to the relevant law-enforcement institutions.

Tip for Trainers: Allow time for questions and answers after the presentation before you move on.

PRESENTATION 3: HOW TO REMOVE BARRIERS AND PROVIDE ADEQUATE SUPPORT TO LGBTIQ CHILD VICTIMS OF BIAS-MOTIVATED BULLYING/VIOLENCE, INCLUDING CYBER-BULLYING

- Maintain confidentiality to build trust.
- Ask open questions about hate as a potential motivation for bullying and violence.
- Don't assume everyone you deal with is cisgender or straight.
- Don't assume everyone who reports homophobia is LGBTIQ.
- It is ok to ask what name or gender pronouns someone prefers you to use. If you get it wrong, just apologize briefly and move on.
- Refer to or tell the children about LGBTIQ services.
- Give victims regular updates about any developments in ongoing cases.
- Respect victims' right to have an incident recorded as hate crime, even if you disagree.
- Be clear that a targeted child is never responsible for the violence they receive.
- LGBTIQ children often think they will not be taken seriously if they report an incident. Prove them wrong.
- Do not "out" the reporter or the victim who has trusted you and reported about the incident. Be careful to maintain their confidentiality when you take the information to other responsible parties (institutions). Get an informed consent any time when their personal data has to be provided to the law-enforcement institutions.
- Safeguard personal information, even from family members. Family members perpetrating anti-LGBTIQ domestic abuse, 'honour'-based violence or forced marriage may be implicated in the abuse.
- Do not assume everyone has the same level of literacy.
- Be responsive to requests by service users who feel more comfortable talking to a staff member of a certain gender.
- Offer service information in large print or easy read formats.
- Consider the possibility that domestic abuse or a sexual assault may have an element of hate motivation.
- Involve other professionals (teachers, health and social workers, school psychologists) working directly with the victim so that support measures can be jointly implemented
- Remember that prosecution of the offender is not always an option. Discuss other options with the social services and the police to prevent relapses of the incidents.

ACTIVITY 3: CODE OF CONDUCT EXERCISE

This is the concluding exercise of the training. Divide participants into small groups. Give them the text of the exercise below. Ask each group to read through, and work through the exercise together. Allow 20 min for group work, then ask a presenter from each small group to present to the large group.

You are staff members of an organisation, for example, a school, a hospital, a clinic, or an NGO. It is up to group participants to decide on the exact type of organisation. The head of management wants you to prepare a plan in order to make your organization more friendly, safe and accessible to LGBTIQ children. You don't have an additional budget for that – you will have to make a plan with no, or very limited financial cost. Your plan take into consideration both the kind of services provided (educational, social, or health services) and the sector in which you are working (public or private/civil society). You have 20 min to brainstorm and write down the key elements of your plan. Appoint a speaker who will present your plan to the large group.

Tip for Trainers: after the small group presentations, ask participants to identify which elements are common to all plans. Write these common elements on a flip chart.

Session 3 resources for preparation and/or additional study:

- Amnesty International (n.d.). First, do no harm: Ensuring the rights of children born intersex. Retrieved from: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/campaigns/2017/05/intersex-rights/>
- European Commission (2019, October). Special Eurobarometer 493 Discrimination in the EU in 2019, European Union. Retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/commfrontoffice/publicopinion/index.cfm/Survey/getSurveyDetail/search/Discrimination/surveyKy/2251>
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights FRA (2015). The fundamental rights situation of intersex people, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Retrieved from: https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2015-focus-04-intersex_en.pdf
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights FRA (2020). EU-LGBTI II. A long way to go for LGBTI equality, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Retrieved from: https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2020-lgbti-equality-1_en.pdf
- ILGA Europe (2020). Annual review of the human rights situation of lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, and intersex people covering the period of January to December 2019. Brussels. Retrieved from: <https://www.ilga-europe.org/sites/default/files/Annual%20Review%202020.pdf>
- ILGA Europe (2020). Rainbow Index 2020. Retrieved from: <https://www.ilga-europe.org/sites/default/files/Attachments/ilgaeurope-rainbowindex-2020-interactive.pdf>
- OII Europe (2019). #MyIntersexStory – Personal accounts by intersex people living in Europe. Retrieved from: https://oiieurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/testimonial_broch_21-21cm_for_web.pdf
- Poirier, J. M., Fisher, S. K., Hunt, R. A., & Bearse, M. (2014). A guide for understanding, supporting, and affirming LGBTIQ2-S children, youth, and families. Washington, DC: American Institutes for Research. Retrieved from: https://www.air.org/sites/default/files/downloads/report/A_Guide_for_Understanding_Supporting_and_Affirming_LGBTIQ2-S_Children_Youth_and_Families.pdf
- The Yogyakarta Principles Plus 10. Additional principles and state obligations on the application of international human rights law in relation to sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression and sex characteristics to complement the Yogyakarta Principles as adopted on 10 November 2017, Geneva. Retrieved from: http://yogyakartaprinciples.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/A5_yogyakartaWEB-2.pdf
- United Nations - Office of the High Commissioner (n.d.). Fact sheet . Intersex. Retrieved from: <https://www.unfe.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/UNFE-Intersex.pdf>

CLOSING SESSION. WRAP-UP AND EVALUATION

ACTIVITY 1: PLENARY DISCUSSION

- Arrange trainees in a circle, so they can all have eye-contact with each other.
- Ask trainees if their fears and/or expectations (see Session 1) for the training have been realised, and if so, ask them to explain how. Encourage trainees to talk freely, but do not put pressure on any individual trainee, e.g., by calling on them individually to respond.
- Encourage trainees to reflect on their experience of the training: Did they learn something new, and if yes, what did they learn? Has anything surprised them or challenged them in any way. If yes, what? What will they take with them (e.g., new knowledge, enhanced skills, new ways of thinking, new friends, etc.) when they leave the workshop?
- Ask all participants to reflect on how the workshop will improve the quality of services provided by them to LGBTIQ children.

ACTIVITY 2: EVALUATION

Trainees will be asked to evaluate the workshop, to provide trainers with valuable feedback that can be used to make changes or adaptations to further improve the learning process and to ensure the workshop's objectives are more effectively reached.

Guidelines for trainers:

- Distribute all trainees a copy of the Evaluation Form (ANNEX 5).
- Ask trainees to read through the form, and whether they need any clarification(s) before filling it in.
- Stress the importance of feedback and the anonymity of the data collected.

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1.

HANDOUT “5 QUESTIONS ON UNDERSTANDING”

1. The terms “sexual orientation”, “gender identity” and “sex characteristics” are:

- Synonyms, as they all refer to a person’s specific set of characteristics
- Different, and they are not necessarily related nor does each one imply anything about the others (correct answer)
- Different, but they are related and each one necessarily implies something about the others

2. “Maria is a trans woman” means:

- Maria identifies as a woman, but her gender identity is male.
- Maria identifies as a woman: her gender identity is female. However, at birth her assigned sex was male. (correct answer)
- Maria has both male and female sex characteristics, but she has chosen to identify as a woman.

3. The fact that someone is intersex:

- Will not necessarily become apparent: it is possible that some intersex people never find out at all.
- Will necessarily become apparent at prenatal stage or at birth at the latest, as soon as it becomes clearly visible to medical staff.
- Will necessarily become apparent, but this could be at different times in life: at birth, during childhood, in puberty or even in adulthood. (correct answer)

4. When speaking with transgender children, the teacher / health worker / social worker should:

- Refer to them with their legal name because this is what is required in their role as a service-provider.
- Be aware both of the trans child’s legal name and the name the trans child has chosen for themselves and ask them which name should be used in public.
- Refer to them with the name that the trans child has chosen for themselves. (correct answer)

5. Asking about the pronouns that should be used when speaking with a trans / intersex child:

- Is not necessary because as a professional, I am obliged to refer to them with the pronoun that suits their legal name.
- Is a necessary first step for creating trust between the teacher/social/health worker and the trans/intersex child. (correct answer)
- It is not considered correct to ask about the pronouns that others prefer to use for themselves. Instead, we should always speak to students/patients using the polite form in plural.

ANNEX 2.

HANDOUT “5 QUESTIONS ON BELIEFS”

Do you **agree** or **disagree** with the following statements? Explain why.

1. Knowing that a student/participant/patient is lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans or intersex has no affect on my role at work.
2. A teacher / health / social / children’s services worker should always use the word “parent” instead of “mother/father” when asking their students / participants / patients about their family relations.
3. I should always ask about the sexual orientation / gender identity of a student/participant/patient who tells me about a bullying incident that happened to them in the school.
4. The LGBTIQ perspective should be an integral part of every teacher/health worker/social/children’s services worker’s professional training.
5. When speaking about LGBTIQ people, professionals need to be aware that there are social disadvantages and challenges that may not be completely visible to others.

ANNEX 3.

HANDOUT “TWENTY KEY CONCEPTS”

No	Term	Definition
1	Bodily integrity	“Everyone, including children, has the right to autonomy and self-determination over their own body, and the only person with the right to make a decision about one’s body is oneself—no one else. This is the principle of bodily integrity, which upholds everyone’s right to be free from acts against their body which they did not consent to. Practices that violate a person’s bodily integrity can range from piercing a baby girl’s ears or being exposed to toxic chemicals without one’s knowledge, to forms of violence such as rape or medical treatment administered against a patient’s wishes. Children are disproportionately vulnerable to violations of their bodily integrity because most violations happen at very young age when a person is unable to speak up for and defend themselves, or give—or refuse—consent”. ^[2]
2	Cisgender or Cis	“Cisgender or Cis is a term used to describe non-trans people. It is used in the same way as heterosexual is used to mean non-homosexual”. ^[3]
3	Coming out	Coming out is “the process of revealing the identification of a lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans or intersex person”. ^[4] With intersex people a coming out is not about identity it is instead “making public”/“sharing information” about having an intersex body, regardless of whether there is also an intersex identity.
4	DSD – Disorders of Sex Development (or Differences of Sex Development)	“The term DSD was introduced in 2006 and has since then been used by medical professionals to refer to intersex bodies. Some intersex people use these terms when referring to themselves. A growing number of intersex people consider DSD terminology to be stigmatizing and prefer to use the term intersex”. ^[5]
5	Gender	“Gender traditionally refers to a social and cultural construct of being a man or a woman. However, some people do not identify within the gender binary of man/woman. Gender exists independently of sex, and an individual’s gender does not always correspond with the sex assigned at birth”. ^[6]
6	Gender affirmation surgery (sex reassignment surgery)	“Surgery to change primary and/or secondary sex characteristics to affirm a person’s gender identity”. ^[7]

7	Gender expression	“Gender Expression is the external manifestations of gender, expressed through a person’s name, pronouns, clothing, haircut, behaviour, voice or body characteristics. Society identifies these cues as masculine or feminine, although what is considered masculine and feminine changes over time and varies by culture”. [8]
8	Gender identity	“Gender Identity is a person’s inner sense of their gender. For trans people, their own internal gender identity does not match the sex they were assigned at birth. Most people have a gender identity of man or woman (or boy or girl), but for some people it does not fit neatly into one of those two choices. Unlike gender expression, gender identity is not visible to others”. [9]
9	“Hermaphrodite”	“An out-of-date term often used to describe intersex people. Today it is generally considered derogatory”. [10]
10	Homophobia	The irrational hatred and fear of LGBTIQ+ people. Homophobia includes prejudice, discrimination, harassment, and acts of violence brought on by fear and hatred. It occurs on personal, institutional, and societal levels. [11]
11	Intersex	“A term that relates to a range of physical traits or variations that lie between stereotypical ideals of male and female. Intersex people are born with physical, hormonal or genetic features that are neither wholly female nor wholly male; or a combination of female and male; or neither female nor male. Many forms of intersex exist; it is a spectrum or umbrella term, rather than a single category. That is why intersex activists frequently prefer to use the term sex characteristics (for example, when talking about grounds that can be protected against discrimination). There is not one static state called ‘intersex status’, so using the term sex characteristics reflects the fact that being intersex is a bodily experience and only one part of a person’s identity”. [12]
12	Intersexphobia	Negative attitudes and feelings towards people who are believed to possess biological sex traits that are not typically male or female, known as Intersex Traits (whether they are born with them or simply exhibit a non-binary gender identity or expression which is commonly associated with having congenital Intersex Traits). [13]
13	Legal gender recognition	“Legal Gender Recognition is the official procedure to change a trans person’s name and gender identifier in official registries and documents such as their birth certificate, ID card, passport or driving license. In some countries, it’s impossible to have your gender recognised by law. In other countries, the procedure is often long, difficult and humiliating”. [14]
14	Sex	“The combination of a person’s bodily characteristics including: chromosomes, hormones, internal and external reproductive organs, and secondary sex characteristics. In most countries this is still limited to the binary of female and male, which can exclude intersex people”. [15]

15	Sex characteristics / Variations of sex characteristics	<p>“Sex Characteristics is a term that refers to a person’s primary sex characteristics such as: chromosomes, anatomy, hormonal structure and reproductive organs or a person’s secondary sex characteristics which become apparent at puberty such as: breasts, facial and pubic hair, Adam’s apple, muscle mass, stature and fat distribution. The term ‘variations of sex characteristics’, therefore, is seen by many activists as a more accurate term than ‘intersex status’, as it refers to a spectrum of possible characteristics instead of a single homogenous status or experience of being intersex”.[16]</p>
16	Sexual orientation	<p>“Sexual orientation: refers to each person’s capacity for profound affection, emotional and sexual attraction to, and intimate and sexual relations with, individuals of a different gender or the same gender or more than one gender”.[17]</p>
17	Trans / Transgender	<p>“Transgender or Trans is an umbrella term which includes those people who have a gender identity which is different to the gender assigned at birth, and those people who wish to portray their gender identity in a different way to the gender assigned at birth. Transgender includes those people who feel they have to, or prefer to, or choose to, whether by language, clothing, accessories, cosmetics or body modification, present themselves differently to the expectations of the gender role assigned to them at birth. This includes, among many others, transsexual and transgender people, transvestites, cross dressers, no gender, multigender, genderqueer people, intersex, and gender variant people who relate to or identify as any of the above”.[18]</p>
18	Transition	<p>Transition is the “period of time when individuals change from the gender role associated with their sex assigned at birth to a different gender role. For many people, this involves learning how to live socially in “the other” gender role; for others this means finding a gender role and expression that is most comfortable for them. Transition may or may not include feminization or masculinization of the body through hormones or other medical procedures. The nature and duration of transition is variable and individualized”.[19]</p> <p>“Transition includes some or all of the following personal, medical, and legal steps: telling one’s family, friends, and co-workers; using a different name and new pronouns; dressing differently; changing one’s name and/or sex on legal documents; hormone therapy; and possibly (though not always) one or more types of surgery. The exact steps involved in transition vary from person to person”.[20]</p>

19	Transphobia	<p>“Transphobia is a matrix of cultural and personal beliefs, opinions, attitudes and aggressive behaviours based on prejudice, disgust, fear and/or hatred directed against individuals or groups who do not conform to, or who transgress societal gender expectations and norms. Transphobia particularly affects individuals whose lived gender identity or gender expression differs from the gender role assigned to them at birth, and it manifests itself in various ways, e.g., as direct physical violence, transphobic speech and insulting, discriminatory media coverage, and social exclusion. Transphobia also includes institutionalized forms of discrimination such as criminalization, pathologization, or stigmatization of non-conforming gender identities and gender expressions”.^[21]</p>
20	Queer	<p>The term “queer” can include, but is not limited to, gay, lesbian, bisexual, transgender, intersex and asexual people. This term has different meanings to different people. Some still find it offensive, while others reclaim it to encompass the broader sense of history of the gay rights movement. Can also be used as an umbrella term like LGBTIQ, as in "the queer community".^[22]</p>

ANNEX 4.

CASE STUDIES

CASE STUDY 1:

K is a bi teenager. He tried to hide his identity from other people in his school because he knew he would receive a lot of backlash. One day he received a message that read “I know your little secret, fag, and I’m going to tell everyone at school unless you do what I say”. The sender of the message then asked for K to provide them with help in their schoolwork: for example, to complete their homework for them, or provide answers to test. After receiving the message, K doesn’t know what to do because he is afraid that if he tries to report the threats, the person will out him.

CASE STUDY 2:

M and J recently became parents of a child that was identified as an intersex person soon after their birth. Doctors suggest the parents should give them their consent in order to perform a number of medical procedures on the child, so the latter will have what they referred to as “a single and clearly defined sex.”. The parents hesitate to make a decision, but the doctors insist, explaining to them that they have no other choice as the child must soon be registered as either male or female. Finally, the parents give their consent.

CASE STUDY 3:

S is a trans woman. When she was born, she was assigned male. She was raised as a boy, but when she was a teenager, she realized she was a woman and she started modifying her gender expression according to her gender identity. She keeps her identity secret from her father, as she is afraid of his reaction, and uses her new identity expression only while at school. At some point, one of the teachers calls her father. The teacher outs S, and summons the father to attend a meeting with the principal, along with S. The principal warns S that she will be expelled “if she does not start dressing according to her sex”, and tells her to “stop confusing other students with her attitude”.

CASE STUDY 4:

During a talk show an actor says the following “... gays spread AIDS among themselves, but not all gays are only homosexual, some are bi and they can spread it among us. It doesn't work in the interest of society”. After an investigation, the Commission for Protection against Discrimination (CPD) finds that the actor has not acted in a discriminatory fashion. Subsequently, this decision is overturned in two court hearings – at the Administrative Court of Sofia City and at the Supreme Administrative Court. The case is then remanded for a new ruling by the CPD.

CASE STUDY 5:

Baby Sarah was born on December 9, 2019 in Spain in the family of a Bulgarian and a British woman born in Gibraltar. At birth, the child was given a birth certificate that listed both her mothers, but without specifying who the child's biological mother was (an example of good practice from Spain, which takes into account the child's relationship with both parents). Under current Spanish law, the child cannot acquire Spanish citizenship because neither mother is a Spanish citizen. The girl was also denied British citizenship because under current British law, her Gibraltarian mother cannot transfer citizenship. The next option was to apply for citizenship for baby Sarah in Bulgaria. However, Bulgarian legislation does not recognize same sex unions, meaning that two persons of the same sex cannot be registered as the parents of a child. Because of this, the Bulgarian authorities refused to issue a birth certificate indicating that the parents are both women, despite the fact that both parents have provided a valid EU birth certificate. This left baby S at risk of statelessness. It also meant that, without having any documentation, she could not leave Spain.

CASE STUDY 6:

G is a very active LGBT+ activist and well-known in the civil society sector. G uses social media to advocate for the human rights of LGBTIQ people and has a substantial following. One day, somebody leaves graffiti on the building where G lives reading "G – faggot. You will hang by a rope". A similar thing has recently happened to another activist called D, on the building where he works. On this occasion, the graffiti read, "D – faggot, you are going to eat wood." The two incidents look to be linked, as the graffiti is written in the same font.

ANNEX 5.

EVALUATION FORM

No	Question	Totally Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Totally agree
1	The objectives of the training workshop have been met.	1	2	3	4	5
2	The training was interactive and encouraged participation.	1	2	3	4	5
3	A variety of training techniques was used.	1	2	3	4	5
4	It was easy to follow the workshop's structure and content.	1	2	3	4	5
5	The training materials (handouts) were useful and relevant to the topics covered.	1	2	3	4	5
6	The length of the workshop was sufficient to cover the material.	1	2	3	4	5
8	The training venue was appropriate.	1	2	3	4	5
9	Practical issues (e.g., electronic equipment for presentations and projections, stationery, catering) were appropriately handled.	1	2	3	4	5
10	Trainer had strong training skills.	1	2	3	4	5
11	Trainer had the knowledge and/or experience about the topics they examined.	1	2	3	4	5

№	Open-ended questions
12	Do you think the quality of the services you provide LGBTIQ children will be improved after having taken part in this workshop? If yes, in what way? If not, why?
13	Will you use what you have learned in your daily practice? If so, how will you make use of it. If not, explain why.
14	Would you recommend this training to your colleagues?

REFERENCES

1	Secondary victimisation occurs when the victim suffers further harm not as a direct result of the criminal act but due to the manner in which institutions and other individuals deal with the victim. Secondary victimisation may be caused, for instance, by repeated exposure of the victim to the perpetrator, repeated interrogation about the same facts, the use of inappropriate language or insensitive comments made by all those who come into contact with victims. Retrieved from: https://eige.europa.eu/thesaurus/terms/1358
2	Definition provided by: Child Rights International Network (CRIN). "Bodily integrity". Retrieved from: https://home.crin.org/issues/bodily-integrity
3	Definition provided by: TGEU (2016). Glossary. Retrieved from: https://tgeu.org/glossary/
4	Definition provided by: ILGA Europe (2015). Glossary. Retrieved from: https://www.ilga-europe.org/sites/default/files/glossary_october_2015_edition.pdf
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